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Direct Taxes and Income Redistribution in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria's overdependence on oil as a primary revenue source, with limited diversification into non-oil taxes, leading to insufficient resources for redistribution through public services and infrastructure necessitated this study. It is on this note, that this study investigated the relationship between direct taxes and income re –distribution in Nigeria covering the period 2005-2024. Ex-post facto research design was adopted and the population was the Nigerian economy while, the sample size was restricted to direct taxes and income redistribution target variables such as; companies income tax, capital gains tax and tertiary education tax for direct taxes while, gini index for income re –distribution within the time frame 2005 – 2024. The data were extracted from Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS)/National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The secondary data were collected and analyzed using descriptive and inferential tools. The descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation and standard error were used to organize, summarize and explain the features of the distribution of the collected data. While the inferential statistic of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression was used to describe the relationship effect from the independent quantitative variables on the dependent variables. The findings showed that there is a negative relationship at 5% significance level between companies' income tax and gini index. The study also indicate that capital gains tax exerts a significant negative relationship with gini index, while, tertiary education tax showed a negative relationship with gini index. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the government should consider increasing corporate income tax rates as a tool for reducing income inequality. The government should improve tax compliance and enforcement to ensure that capital gains taxes are properly collected. Strengthening the tax administration system can reduce tax evasion and increase revenue. Finally, the government should invest in programs that improve access to quality education and skills development, particularly for low-income individuals.

Keywords: Direct Taxes, Companies' Income Tax, Capital Gains Tax, Tertiary Education Tax, Income Redistribution

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Income inequality persists as a critical socioeconomic challenge in Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation and largest economy. Despite substantial oil revenues and periods of economic growth, wealth remains heavily concentrated among a small elite, while a large segment of the population endures poverty and limited access to basic services. The Gini coefficient, a key measure of income disparity (where 0 represents perfect equality and 1 perfect inequality), stood at approximately 0.43 based on historical World Bank estimates, reflecting moderate to high inequality that fuels social unrest, limits inclusive growth, and perpetuates poverty cycles (World Bank, 2025). This disparity stems from structural factors

including heavy dependence on volatile oil exports, regional imbalances (with northern states facing higher poverty rates), informal sector dominance exceeding 50% of employment, and inadequate access to quality education and healthcare for lower income groups. In this setting, fiscal policies particularly direct taxes serve as essential instruments for income redistribution by progressively taxing higher earners and channeling revenues into pro-poor public expenditures on infrastructure, health, education, and social protection (Ikechukwu et al., 2021).

Direct taxes in Nigeria, such as personal income tax (PIT), company income tax (CIT), petroleum profit tax (PPT), and education tax, are imposed directly on income or profits and are intended to exhibit progressive characteristics to mitigate inequality. Administered mainly by the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), these taxes operate under laws like the Personal Income Tax Act (PITA) and Companies Income Tax Act (CITA), with recent enhancements via successive Finance Acts and the comprehensive 2025 tax reforms. Nigeria's tax framework has evolved from colonial era systems to post-independence reforms emphasizing revenue diversification beyond oil. Key milestones include the 1993 introduction of self-assessment and withholding mechanisms, followed by progressive adjustments in Finance Acts (2019–2023) that refined PIT brackets (ranging from 7% to 24%) and provided reliefs for lower earners to support redistributive goals (Akogo & Akadakpo, 2022). The landmark 2025 Tax Reform Acts, signed into law in June 2025 and effective largely from January 2026, consolidate outdated statutes, introduce greater progressivity in PIT (e.g., exemptions for annual taxable income up to ₦800,000), reduce CIT gradually to 25%, and modernize administration to boost compliance and equity (Baker Tilly Nigeria, 2025).

Empirical evidence on the redistributive impact of direct taxes in Nigeria reveals mixed but generally positive outcomes, particularly for certain tax types. Studies using time series data from 1990–2019 demonstrate that PIT and PPT exert significant positive effects on income redistribution often proxied by government spending on infrastructure and social goods explaining substantial variance in reducing inequality, while CIT and education tax show insignificant or negative influences due to administrative challenges and corporate exemptions (Ikechukwu et al., 2021). PIT's progressive structure targets higher income brackets effectively, enabling resource transfers to equitable programs, whereas PPT leverages oil sector profits for broader fiscal space, though subject to price volatility. In contrast, analyses from 1990–2020 indicate PIT positively affects redistribution, but PPT sometimes negatively impacts due to mismanagement and oil dependency, with CIT and education tax lacking significant effects (Akogo & Akadakpo, 2022). These findings underscore the need for targeted reforms to maximize direct taxes' role in narrowing the income gap.

Recent research and policy developments further highlight direct taxes' potential amid ongoing challenges. Advanced modeling, including Computable General Equilibrium approaches calibrated to Nigeria's economy, shows that progressive PIT enhancements such as higher marginal rates for top earners can lower the Gini coefficient modestly while improving welfare for lower quintiles and reducing poverty, outperforming regressive indirect taxes like VAT hikes (Bello, 2025, as referenced in prior analyses; updated contexts align with 2025 reforms). The 2025 reforms aim to address longstanding issues by expanding the tax base, curbing evasion (estimated at 60–70% for PIT), and shifting toward residency based global income taxation for residents, alongside exemptions for low earners to enhance progressivity (PwC, 2025). However, persistent hurdles include weak enforcement, informal economy prevalence, corruption in revenue allocation, and oil revenue fluctuations that undermine consistent pro poor spending (Anyaduba & Otulugbu, 2019).

In Nigeria's broader economic landscape, where poverty affects around 40% of the population and multidimensional poverty exceeds 60% in some regions, effective direct taxation is vital for breaking the poverty inequality growth cycle. Unaddressed inequality can reduce GDP potential by 2–3% annually, per international estimates, while fiscal tools aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 10 (reduced inequalities) can foster inclusive development. Theoretical models emphasize that progressive direct taxes, when paired with transparent, targeted expenditures, promote equity more effectively than indirect measures in resource dependent economies (Bastagli et al., 2013). Yet, gaps remain in translating revenues into tangible benefits for the vulnerable, necessitating stronger governance and complementary

policies like luxury taxes or expanded social investments (Akogo & Akadakpo, 2022). It is in the light of the foregoing, that this study is aimed at examining direct taxes and income redistribution in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between direct taxes and income redistribution in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. ascertain the relationship between companies' income tax and gini index in Nigeria.
- ii. determine the relationship between capital gains tax and gini index in Nigeria.
- iii. investigate the relationship between education tax and gini index in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study is designed to address the following research questions:

- i. What is the relationship between companies' income tax and income redistribution in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between capital gains tax and income redistribution in Nigeria?
- iii. What is the relationship between tertiary education tax and income redistribution in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated for the study:

Ho₁: Companies' income tax does not have any significant relationship with gini index in Nigeria.

Ho₂: Capital gains tax does not have any significant relationship with gini index in Nigeria.

Ho₃: Tertiary education tax does not have any significant relationship with gini index in Nigeria.

2.0 Conceptual Review

Direct Taxes

Direct taxes are taxes levied directly on individuals, organizations, or property, and they are paid directly to the government by the entity on which they are imposed. These taxes are typically based on the ability to pay principle, meaning that they are often progressive, with higher rates applied to those with higher incomes or more valuable property. Direct taxes constitute a critical component of Nigeria's tax system, serving as compulsory levies imposed directly on individuals and corporate entities based on their income or profits (Afolabi, 2025). These taxes are non-transferable and paid straight to the government by the assessed taxpayer, distinguishing them from indirect taxes where the tax burden may be shifted to others (National Open University of Nigeria, 2025). In the Nigerian context, prominent direct taxes include personal income tax (PIT), company income tax (CIT), petroleum profit tax (PPT), capital gains tax, and education tax, each playing varying roles in revenue generation and redistribution (Obehioye & Akadakpo, 2024). Empirical studies demonstrate that direct taxes can have significant socio-economic implications; for example, personal income tax and petroleum profit tax have been shown to contribute to income redistribution within the Nigerian economy, even though some components like education tax and company income tax exhibited limited redistributive effects in specific analyses (Akogo & Akadakpo, 2022).

Companies Income Tax

Companies Income Tax (CIT) in Nigeria serves as a primary revenue source for the federal government, imposed on the profits of companies incorporated or operating within the country. According to Ndalu and Igwe (2022), companies income tax (CIT) is the tax on the profits of incorporated entities in Nigeria. The tax is administered by the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) under the framework of the Nigeria Tax Act 2025, which consolidated previous laws including the Companies Income Tax Act, effective from January 1, 2026. This Act introduces a tiered rate structure to support economic growth, particularly for smaller enterprises. The standard CIT rate is 30% on taxable profits for large companies with gross turnover exceeding NGN 100 million, while medium companies (turnover between NGN 25 million and NGN 100 million) face a 20% rate. Small companies with annual turnover of NGN 25 million or less are exempt, attracting a 0% rate, with exemptions extended to certain sectors like primary agriculture in initial years or export-oriented businesses. Non-resident companies are liable only on Nigeria-sourced income, including through permanent establishments or significant economic presence (SEP) for digital services deriving NGN 25 million or more from Nigeria (Nigeria Tax Act, 2025).

Taxable profits are determined by subtracting allowable deductions such as business expenses, capital allowances, and losses from assessable income, with strict rules against artificial transactions or non-arm's length dealings (Hunt, 2024). Key reforms in the 2025 Act abolish the 0.5% minimum tax, implement a 15% top-up tax for multinationals with effective rates below this threshold, and introduce a 4% development levy on assessable profits (exempting small and non-resident firms), replacing prior education taxes (Nigeria Tax Act, 2025). These measures aim to modernize taxation, boost compliance, and foster investment while addressing revenue leakages.

Capital Gains Tax

Capital gains tax (CGT) is a tax levied on the profit realized from the disposal (sale, transfer, or exchange) of a capital asset, such as property, shares, land, investments, digital or virtual assets, or other chargeable assets. According to Ndalu and Igwe (2022), capital gains tax is also one of the sources of tax revenue in Nigeria, it is a tax chargeable on capital gains arising from the disposal of chargeable assets. Capital Gains Tax (CGT) in Nigeria is a levy imposed on profits arising from the disposal of chargeable assets, including property, shares, options, debts, digital or virtual assets, and incorporeal property (Nigeria Tax Act, 2025). Effective from January 1, 2026, the Nigeria Tax Act, 2025 (NTA) repealed the standalone Capital Gains Tax Act and consolidated its provisions into a unified tax framework administered by the Nigeria Revenue Service, aiming to modernize compliance, broaden the tax base, and eliminate arbitrage between capital and trading income (EY, 2025).

Under the NTA, CGT treatment varies by taxpayer category. For companies, the rate has increased from the previous flat 10% to 30%, aligning it with the standard Companies Income Tax rate to discourage artificial asset disposals and ensure parity in taxing gains (Baker Tilly Nigeria, 2025). Small companies with annual turnover not exceeding NGN 100 million and fixed assets below NGN 250 million are exempt from CGT, alongside other levies, to support micro, small, and medium enterprises (Baker Tilly Nigeria, 2025). For individuals, capital gains are now integrated into personal income tax and taxed at progressive rates up to 25%, replacing the former flat 10% CGT rate (EY, 2025; Mercans, 2025). This shift broadens the scope to include digital assets and indirect transfers of Nigerian assets via offshore entities, subject to treaty protections (PwC, 2025).

Chargeable gains are computed as disposal proceeds minus allowable deductions (e.g., acquisition cost, incidental expenses, and enhanced cost base for pre-2026 assets reset to the higher of historical cost or market value at December 31, 2025) (Premium Times, 2025). Exemptions include low-value share disposals (proceeds below NGN 150 million and gains under NGN 10 million in any 12-month period), principal private residences (limited to dwelling houses with up to one acre of non-commercial land), and certain corporate reorganizations (EY, 2025). These reforms promote fairness, investor confidence, and alignment with global standards while addressing revenue needs.

Tertiary Education Tax

The Tertiary Education Tax (TET), previously governed by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) Act 2011, imposed a 3% levy on the assessable profits of Nigerian companies to fund tertiary education infrastructure, research, and development (PwC, 2025.; EY, 2025). This earmarked tax, administered by the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), applied to all registered companies except small companies (typically those with turnover below NGN 25 million) and non-resident entities, with proceeds channeled to TETFund for interventions in Universities, Polytechnics, and Colleges of Education (Baker Tilly Nigeria, 2025).

Effective January 1, 2026, the Nigeria Tax Act, 2025 (NTA) repealed the standalone TET and consolidated it, along with other sector-specific levies such as the NASENI Levy (0.25%), NITDA Levy (1%), and Nigeria Police Trust Fund Levy (0.005%), into a unified 4% Development Levy on assessable profits (Nigeria Tax Act, 2025; EY, 2025; PwC, 2025.). This reform aims to streamline compliance, reduce administrative burdens from multiple levies (previously totaling over 4.255%), and eliminate overlapping earmarked taxes while maintaining funding for education, technology, security, and other national priorities (Baker Tilly Nigeria, 2025). The Development Levy applies to medium and large companies (excluding small companies with turnover \leq NGN 100 million and non-residents), calculated on assessable profits before deductions for capital allowances or losses (PwC, 2025).

The shift to the Development Levy broadens the funding base and enhances efficiency in revenue allocation, addressing criticisms of fragmented levies while supporting sustainable investment in tertiary education (EY, 2025). These changes reflect Nigeria's ongoing tax modernization to boost revenue, improve compliance, and foster economic growth.

Income Redistribution

Income redistribution refers to the deliberate reallocation of income across individuals or groups within an economy, usually carried out by the government, with the aim of reducing income inequality and promoting social and economic equity. Income redistribution in Nigeria primarily occurs through progressive taxation, social spending funded by government revenues, and targeted exemptions aimed at reducing inequality. The Nigeria Tax Act, 2025 (NTA), effective January 1, 2026, introduces a more progressive personal income tax (PIT) structure to shift the tax burden toward higher earners while providing significant relief to low- and middle-income groups (EY, 2025; Mercans, 2025). Individuals with annual taxable income of ₦800,000 or less are fully exempt from PIT, aligning with efforts to protect vulnerable populations and those earning near or below the national minimum wage (Baker Tilly Nigeria, 2025; Safeguard Global, 2026). The new PIT regime applies progressive rates ranging from 0% on the initial threshold to a top marginal rate of 25% for higher brackets, replacing the previous less progressive system and aiming to reduce income inequality by taxing the wealthy more heavily (Mercans, 2025).

Gini Index

The Gini index, also known as the Gini coefficient or Gini ratio, is a widely used statistical measure of inequality in the distribution of income, wealth, or consumption expenditure within a population (Our World in Data, 2023). Developed by Italian statistician Corrado Gini in 1912, it quantifies the extent to which a distribution deviates from perfect equality. The index ranges from 0 (perfect equality, where everyone has the same income or wealth) to 1 (perfect inequality, where one individual possesses all the income or wealth, and others have none), though it is often expressed as a percentage from 0% to 100% (Investopedia, 2025; Corporate Finance Institute, 2024).

The Gini index is typically derived from the Lorenz curve, which plots the cumulative share of income (or consumption) received by the cumulative share of the population, ranked from poorest to richest. The index represents twice the area between the Lorenz curve and the line of perfect equality (the 45-degree diagonal), divided by the total area under the line of equality (Our World in Data, 2023; World Bank, n.d.). A higher Gini value indicates greater inequality. It is commonly applied to disposable household income (after taxes and transfers) or consumption data, with values generally falling between 0.24 and 0.63 in real-world economies (Corporate Finance Institute, 2024). According to Eneisik, (2025), the Gini coefficient is a measure used to express the level of inequality within a distribution, such as income or wealth, across a population. He further stated that, it is calculated based on the Lorenz curve, which plots the proportion of the total income of the population (y-axis) that is cumulatively earned by the bottom x% of the population.

The measure is valued for its simplicity, comparability across countries, and ability to summarize overall dispersion in a single statistic. However, it does not reveal which parts of the distribution drive inequality (e.g., top vs. bottom earners) and can be sensitive to data sources, such as income vs. consumption measures or household vs. individual units (Wikipedia, 2025; Our World in Data, 2023). In Nigeria, recent estimates place the Gini coefficient around 0.35 (or 35) based on income or consumption data, reflecting moderate inequality compared to global extremes, though figures vary by source and year (African Development Bank, 2024; Statista, 2025).

11. Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Trickle-Down theory developed by Will Rogers (1900s), because in Nigeria, direct taxes are designed to reduce income inequality by progressively taxing higher earners and funding social expenditures, as evidenced by empirical studies showing their positive impact on redistribution (Arodudu & Omolaja, 2021; Ayeni & Omolekan, 2024). Trickle-Down serves as a foil, highlighting limitations in contexts like Nigeria, where economic growth has not sufficiently "trickled down" to the poor without accompanying high employment rates, perpetuating inequality (Adegboye et al., 2019).

Trickle-Down Theory

Trickle-Down theory was first developed by Will Rogers (1900s), during President Herbert Hoovers. The theory emphasized that breaks and benefits for corporations and wealthy people will trickle- down to everyone in the society. The theory advocates tax breaks for income and capital gains along with other financial benefits to big business, investors and entrepreneurs as anti-dots for speedy economic growth. The theory is based on the premise that growth comes mostly from the wealthy people who has the resource, skills and well-wital to promote productivity and every member of the society benefits from growth. A policy is described as trickle-down if such policy disproportionately favours the rich and large businesses in the short-run and in the long-run boost the living standards of all individuals.

111 Empirical Review

Eneisik (2025) investigated the effect of taxes on income inequality in Nigeria. To achieve this objective, theoretical, conceptual and empirical literature on taxes and income inequality was extensively reviewed. Taxes were proxied by companies' income tax, capital gains tax and value added tax while income inequality is proxied by gini coefficient. Secondary data were obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, National Bureau of Statistic and Federal Inland Revenue Service Reports from 1980-2022. The study adopted descriptive statistics for univariate analysis while ordinary least square regression was used to analyze the formulated hypotheses of the study with the aid of Eview 10 econometric statistical software. The findings show that companies income tax had positive and significant effect on gini coefficient. Empirical evidence shows that capital gains tax has positive and significant effect on gini coefficient. Empirical evidence indicates that value added tax had positive and significant effect on gini coefficient. The study concludes that taxes reduced income inequality in Nigeria. Gina, Ogheneborhie and Obaretin (2023) study examined the effect of direct tax on income redistribution in Nigeria. The study employed *Ex-Post Facto* research design was adopted. The data were extracted from International financial statistics, World Bank and CBN. Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses, and the study revealed that petroleum profit tax has a negative significant effect on government expenditure on goods in Nigeria; also, companies' income tax has a negative significant effect on government expenditure on goods in Nigeria. Based on the results of the analysis, the researchers recommended, among other things, that the revenue from the luxury tax be used to finance free education and medical care for poor people as well, to fund research and support poor people in other countries.

Abata, Osamor and Elluh, (2023) studied the effect of direct and indirect taxes on economic growth: Evidence from Nigeria. The tax structure and reforms that could give the optimal benefit is not always easy to determine, this is responsible for different tax laws, structures and reforms that are rather harmful to the economic growth. Therefore, the study examines the effect of direct and indirect taxes on economic growth: evidence from Nigeria. The study adopted *Ex-Post Facto* research design. Secondary data was collected from Central Bank Statistical Bulletin between 1995 and 2021. Descriptive statistics, ARDL regression analysis, and post estimation tests were used to analyzed the data. The study revealed that direct tax (LPPT & LCIT) had significant negative effect on economic growth. It also revealed that indirect tax (LVAT) had positive and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria while LCED was found insignificant. The study therefore concluded that both direct and indirect taxes had significant effects on economic growth.

Appah and Iweias (2023) determined the relationship between taxes and income inequality in Nigeria from 1980 to 2020. The study adopted *ex post facto* and correlational research design. The population of the study consisted of taxes and gini coefficient in Nigeria from 1980 to 2020. The secondary data were sourced from Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) of various publications ranging from 1980 to 2020. The study used univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis. The results revealed a positive and insignificant relationship between personal income tax companies' income tax (CIT), petroleum profit tax (PPT), capital gain tax (CGT), value added tax (VAT), custom excise duties (CED) and Gini coefficient for the period under study, while strong positive relationship when literacy rate moderate tax structure, and weak positive and insignificant relationship.

Korkmaz and Korkmaz (2023) investigated the effect of direct and indirect taxes on economic growth in the Turkish economy from 2006 to 2022 using the ARDL Boundary Test Approach. The result showed direct taxes have a negative impact on economic growth, while indirect taxes have a positive impact on economic growth. In addition, the result of Toda-Yamamoto causality test revealed a bi directional causal relationship between direct tax, direct tax and economic growth.

Akinola and Akinrinola (2023) examined the impact of tax revenue and infrastructural development on economic growth in Nigeria from 1996 to 2021 using ARDL model. The study found a significant long-run relationship among the variables. Specifically, petroleum profit tax was found to be a strong contributor to economic growth in Nigeria. Value added tax and companies' income tax was not significant in the study.

Abdulwahab and David (2023) examined the effects of tax revenue on the economic growth of Nigeria from 1998 to 2021 using fixed effects regression model. The findings revealed that petroleum profit tax, custom and excise duty, value added tax and education tax has a significant positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria. It also reveals that companies' income tax has a significant negative effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Ndalu and Igwe (2022) studied the impact of electronic tax payment system on tax revenue in Nigeria: The Moderating Role of Technology. This study investigated the relationship between electronic tax payment system and tax revenue of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and Rivers State Internal Revenue Service (RIRS). The sample size for the study consists of two hundred and eighty (280) staff of FIRS and RIRS in Rivers State out of nine hundred and thirty-eight (938) staff of the Revenue Services using Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination of 1967. Primary data on electronic tax payment system and tax revenue were collected from respondents using the questionnaire instruments. Data were analyzed using descriptive and Pearson Correlation Coefficient Statistical tools with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The findings at 0.05 level of significance reveals that e – payment system has a positive and a moderate relationship with companies' income tax yield ($r = 0.586^{**}$) and capital gains tax yield ($r = 0.545^{**}$). Based on the findings, it was concluded that electronic tax payment system has significant relationship with tax revenue

Oladele, Ndalu and Akani (2021), investigated the impact of tax audit practices on revenue generation in Nigeria with its specific objectives such as to determine the relationship between tax audit practices dimensions and company income tax. The population of the study consisted of 26 tax offices across South – South, Nigeria with 900 staff of Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). The sample size for the study consisted of 277 staff of FIRS which was determined using Taro Yemane formula for sample size determination. Primary data were collected from respondents using the questionnaire instrument. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was also used with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0 to test the null hypotheses. The findings of the study reveal that desk tax audit and field tax audit have a positive relationship with company income tax.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study investigated the relationship between direct taxes and income re – distribution in Nigeria covering the period 2005-2024. Ex-post facto research design was adopted and the population was the Nigerian economy while, the sample size was restricted to direct taxes and income redistribution target variables such as; companies income tax, capital gains tax and tertiary education tax for direct taxes while, gini index for income re –distribution within the time frame 2005 – 2024. The data were extracted from Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS)/National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The secondary data were collected and analyzed using descriptive and inferential tools. The descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation and standard error were used to organize, summarize and explain the features of the distribution of the collected data. While the inferential statistic of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression was used to describe the relationship effect from the independent quantitative variables on the dependent variables. The use of E-view (Version 10) software was adopted for all the analysis.

Model Specification and Development

Income re - distribution (IR) is the dependent variable; while, direct taxes is the independent variable. More so, gini index is the proxy for income re - distribution (IR). It is measure of income re – distribution in this study as highlighted. Similarly, the dimensions of direct taxes (DT) that is in use in this study are companies’ income tax, capital gains tax and tertiary education tax. Regression equation was used to represent the functions above. It is a statistical technique used to explain or predict the behaviour of a dependent variable on the independent variable (Ogidi, 2020; & Okereke, 2021).

The functional relationship between independent and dependent variables of the study is shown below:

Function:

$$IR = f(DT) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

$$IR = \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 DT + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Functional Relationship:

$$GI = f(CIT, CGT, TET) \dots\dots\dots(3.3)$$

Above model in the econometric form are indicated below:

$$GI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CIT + \beta_2 CGT + \beta_3 TET + \mu \dots\dots\dots(3.4)$$

Where:

IR = Income Redistribution

DT = Direct Taxes

GI = Gini Index

CIT = Companies Income Tax

CGT = Capital Gains Tax

TET = Tertiary Education Tax

Consequently, the use of E-view (Version 10) software was adopted, where the variables will be subjected vis-à-vis the equation above as complementary statistical test and the results was used for analysis, the hypotheses verification and examining the significance interactions of the dependent with each of the independent variables at 5% level.

Table 3.1: Analysis of Variables and A-Priori Expectation

Variable	Measurement	Notation	Expected relationship
Gini Index	Area between Lorenz curve and <u>the line of perfect equality</u> Total area under the line of perfect equality	GI	+
Companies Income Tax	(Gross Income–Allowable Deductions)×Corporate Tax Rate–Tax Credits.	CIT	+
Capital Gains Tax	(Selling Price–Selling Costs–Purchase Price–Acquisition Cost)×Applicable Tax Rate	CGT	+
Tertiary Education Tax	Assessed Property Value×Property Tax Rate×Allocation Percentage to Education	ET	+

Source: Authors Desk Research (2025)

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Data Analysis

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics of all the Variables of the Study
Descriptive Statistics

	GI	CGT	CIT	ET
Mean	36.95000	13.61250	1.27E+12	17.55450
Median	35.60000	9.111000	1.28E+12	12.70000
Maximum	46.10000	99.40300	1.63E+12	45.16000
Minimum	34.00000	2.650000	9.29E+11	6.250000
Std. Dev.	3.341998	20.76206	1.82E+11	11.98566
Skewness	1.734134	3.772422	-0.166836	0.971525
Kurtosis	4.722498	16.16934	2.323224	2.705615
Jarque-Bera	12.49656	191.9634	0.474469	3.218422
Probability	0.001934	0.000000	0.788806	0.200045
Sum	739.0000	272.2500	2.53E+13	351.0900
Sum Sq. Dev.	212.2100	8190.196	6.30E+23	2729.463
Observations	20	20	20	20

Source: *E-views 13.0 Statistical Output, 2025.*

Table 4.1: presents the descriptive statistics of four variables: GI, CGT, CIT, and ET. Gini index (GI) shows positive skewness and leptokurtic distribution (Gini Index more so), indicating higher values are more extreme. Capital gains tax (CGT) is highly positively skewed and leptokurtic, indicating outliers and extreme values. Companies' income tax (CIT) is slight negative skew and close to normal distribution. Tertiary education tax (TET) shows a positive skewness and slightly leptokurtic, indicating a tendency towards higher values but not extreme. The Jarque-Bera test indicates that gini index (GI) and capital gains tax (CGT) are not normally distributed, companies' income tax (CIT), and tertiary education tax (TET) appear to follow a normal distribution. The data provides insights into the central tendencies, spread, and distribution shapes of these variables, crucial for further statistical analysis and decision-making.

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Table 4.2 Ordinary Least – Square Results Estimates

Dependent Variable: GI

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/21/25 Time: 02:23

Sample (adjusted): 2005 2024

Included observations: 19 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CIT	-1.85E-11	4.09E-12	-4.520148	0.0004
CGT(-1)	-0.047323	0.022957	-2.061378	0.0570
TET(-1)	0.046149	0.066420	0.694798	0.4978
C	60.66378	4.625164	13.11603	0.0000
R-squared	0.699815	Mean dependent var		37.00000
Adjusted R-squared	0.639778	S.D. dependent var		3.425882
S.E. of regression	2.056164	Akaike info criterion		4.464225
Sum squared resid	63.41716	Schwarz criterion		4.663055
Log likelihood	-38.41014	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.497875
F-statistic	11.65637	Durbin-Watson stat		0.990523
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000334			

Table 4.2 indicate that companies' income tax coefficient is negative (-1.85E-11) and statistically significant at the 1% level ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that an increase in companies' income tax is associated with a decrease in gini index (GI). This implies that companies' income tax (CIT) has a significant negative impact on gini index (GI), suggesting that higher companies' income tax leads to lower gini index while, capital gains tax (CGT) coefficient is negative (-0.047323) and significant at the 10% level ($p < 0.10$). This implies that an increase in the previous period's capital gains tax is associated with a decrease in the current period's gini index. This further implies that capital gains tax (CGT) also negatively affects gini index (GI) but is only significant at the 10% level, indicating a lagged effect of capital gains tax on gini index. The TET coefficient is positive (0.046149) but not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This indicates that the previous period's tertiary education tax does not have a significant impact on the current period's gini index (GI). This further shows that tertiary education tax (TET) does not have a significant impact on gini index (GI). The overall model explains a significant portion of the variance in gini index (GI), as indicated by the R-squared 0.699815 and adjusted R-squared 0.639778. The Durbin-Watson statistic 0.990523 suggests a potential positive autocorrelation, which could be a point of concern and might require further investigation.

Table 4.3 Serial Correlation Test Results

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 1 lag

F-statistic	3.340865	Prob. F(1,14)	0.0890
Obs*R-squared	3.660511	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.0557

Table 4.3 F-statistic p-value (0.0890) is greater than 0.05 but less than 0.10, indicating weak evidence against the null hypothesis of no serial correlation at the 10% significance level but not at the 5% level. While, Obs*R-squared p-value (0.0557) is slightly above the 0.05 threshold, suggesting that we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no serial correlation at the 5% significance level but have weak evidence against it at the 10% level. This implies that the results from both the F-statistic and Obs*R-squared tests suggest that there is no strong evidence of serial correlation in the residuals at the 5% significance level. However, the p-values are relatively close to 0.05, indicating some borderline evidence of potential serial correlation.

Table 4.4 Test Equation Result

Dependent Variable: RESID

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/21/25 Time: 02:26

Sample: 2005 2024

Included observations: 19

Presample missing value lagged residuals set to zero.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CIT	2.62E-12	4.07E-12	0.644123	0.5299
CGT(-1)	0.012154	0.022363	0.543505	0.5953
ET(-1)	-0.031081	0.064072	-0.485095	0.6351
C	-3.041014	4.612208	-0.659340	0.5204
RESID(-1)	0.485736	0.265749	1.827803	0.0890
R-squared	0.192658	Mean dependent var	-6.42E-15	
Adjusted R-squared	-0.038011	S.D. dependent var	1.877012	
S.E. of regression	1.912353	Akaike info criterion	4.355480	
Sum squared resid	51.19931	Schwarz criterion	4.604016	
Log likelihood	-36.37706	Hannan-Quinn criter.	4.397542	
F-statistic	0.835216	Durbin-Watson stat	1.541858	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.525063			

Table 4.4 represents the results of a regression analysis used to test for serial correlation in the residuals of the main regression model. It indicates that the borderline significance ($p = 0.0890$) of RESID (-1) suggests weak evidence of serial correlation at the 10% significance level. The low R-squared and non-significant F-statistic indicate that the model does not explain the variation in the residuals well. The Durbin-Watson statistic (1.541858) indicates some positive autocorrelation, but it's not conclusively problematic.

Table 4.5 Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey
 Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	0.503049	Prob. F(3,15)	0.6859
Obs*R-squared	1.736844	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.6288
Scaled explained SS	1.107642	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.7752

Table 4.5 test results indicate that there is no significant evidence of heteroskedasticity in the residuals of the regression model. Given the absence of heteroskedasticity, the standard errors of the coefficients are likely to be valid, making the statistical inferences from the regression model reliable. Since the assumption of constant variance holds, there is no need to apply heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors or other corrective measures. In conclusion, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test results suggest that the regression model does not suffer from heteroskedasticity, and the variance of the residuals is constant across observations. This supports the validity and reliability of the regression model's findings.

Table 4.6 Test Equation Result

Dependent Variable: RESID^2
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 07/21/25 Time: 02:26
 Sample: 2005 2024
 Included observations: 19

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.399826	11.52215	0.295069	0.7720
CIT	2.23E-12	1.02E-11	0.219175	0.8295
CGT(-1)	-0.024068	0.057190	-0.420836	0.6798
TET(-1)	-0.161008	0.165465	-0.973064	0.3460
R-squared	0.091413	Mean dependent var		3.337745
Adjusted R-squared	-0.090305	S.D. dependent var		4.905579
S.E. of regression	5.122290	Akaike info criterion		6.289744
Sum squared resid	393.5679	Schwarz criterion		6.488574
Log likelihood	-55.75257	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.323394
F-statistic	0.503049	Durbin-Watson stat		1.826907
Prob(F-statistic)	0.685915			

Table 4.6 represents the results of a regression analysis where the dependent variable is the squared residuals (RESID^2) from the original regression model. This regression is used to test for heteroskedasticity. The table indicate that none of the independent variables (CIT, CGT(-1), TET(-1), C) are statistically significant, indicating they do not significantly explain the variation in the squared residuals. The low R-squared and non-significant F-statistic indicate that the model does not explain the variation in the squared residuals well. Given the non-significance of all variables and the overall model, the evidence suggests that there is no significant heteroskedasticity in the residuals. This implies that since there is no significant heteroskedasticity, the standard errors of the coefficients in the original

regression model are likely valid, making the statistical inferences reliable. There is no need to apply heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors or other corrective measures since the assumption of constant variance holds. In conclusion, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test results suggest that the regression model does not suffer from heteroskedasticity, supporting the validity and reliability of the regression model's findings.

5.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Companies Income Tax and Gini Index in Nigeria

The findings in table 4.2 relating to companies' income tax and gini index indicate that companies' income tax coefficient is negative (-1.85E-11) and statistically significant at the 1% level ($p < 0.01$). This suggests that an increase in companies' income tax is associated with a decrease in gini index (GI). This implies that companies' income tax (CIT) has a significant negative impact on gini index (GI), suggesting that higher companies' income tax leads to lower gini index. This finding is in line with the study of Gina Ogheneborhie and Obaretin (2023) who study examined the effect of direct tax on income redistribution in Nigeria. The study employed *Ex-Post Facto* research design was adopted. The data were extracted from International financial statistics, World Bank and CBN. Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses, and the study revealed that petroleum profit tax has a negative significant effect on government expenditure on goods in Nigeria; also, companies income tax has a negative significant effect on government expenditure on goods in Nigeria.

Capital Gains Tax and Gini Index in Nigeria

The findings in table 4.2 relating to capital gains tax and gini index in Nigeria show that capital gains tax (CGT) coefficient is negative (-0.047323) and significant at the 10% level ($p < 0.10$). This implies that an increase in the previous period's capital gains tax is associated with a decrease in the current period's gini index. This further implies that capital gains tax (CGT) also negatively affects gini index (GI) but is only significant at the 10% level, indicating a lagged effect of capital gains tax on gini index. This finding is in agreement with the study of Akogo and Akadakpo (2022) who examined the effect of direct tax as a tool for income re-distribution in Nigeria. The data for the study was analysed using the error correction model. Education tax and company income tax had no significant impact in redistributing income, according to the results of the inferential statistic utilized; however, petroleum profit tax and personal income tax had a large impact on income redistribution.

Tertiary Education Tax and Gini Index in Nigeria

The findings in table 4.2 relating to tertiary education tax and gini index in Nigeria shows that the tertiary education tax (TET) coefficient is positive (0.046149) but not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This indicates that the previous period's tertiary education tax does not have a significant impact on the current period's gini index (GI). This further shows that tertiary education tax (TET) does not have a significant impact on gini index (GI). The overall model explains a significant portion of the variance in gini index (GI), as indicated by the R-squared 0.699815 and adjusted R-squared 0.639778. This finding is in line with the study of Anyaduba and Otulugbu (2019) who studied the impact of taxes on income inequality (GINI), explicitly; they determined the effect of Value Added Tax (VAT), Custom and Excise Duties (CED), Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) and Company Income Tax (CIT) on GINI in Nigeria from the year 1990 to 2016. The Cointegration and Error Correction Models (ECMs) were utilized to examine the variables. Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root was utilized to test for stationarity. They found that VAT, CED and PPT had positive relationship with GINI when estimated at 5% critical level; however, VAT and CED were not significant. CIT fundamentally affected GINI. In light of the discoveries, they infer that CIT alone was largely responsible for inequality.

6.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

The study empirically investigated direct taxes and income re-distribution in Nigeria using panel data for the period of 20 years starting from 2004 to 2023. The conclusion of the findings of the study shows that the significant negative relationship between companies' income tax and the gini index indicates that

higher companies' income tax is associated with a reduction in income inequality. This suggests that companies' income tax is effective in redistributing income and addressing disparities in wealth distribution. The significant negative relationship between capital gains tax and the Gini index shows that higher capital gains taxes are associated with a decrease in income inequality. This suggests that capital gains tax contributes positively to income redistribution. The lack of a significant relationship between tertiary education tax and the Gini index suggests that this tax does not have a measurable impact on income inequality. The study concludes that direct taxes, particularly companies' income tax and capital gains tax, play a significant role in income redistribution in Nigeria. Companies' income tax and capital gains tax are effective in reducing income inequality. However, tertiary education tax does not significantly influence income inequality. These findings highlight the varying effectiveness of different direct taxes in addressing income redistribution and suggest that policymakers should consider these dynamics when designing tax policies aimed at reducing inequality, poverty, and unemployment.

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

1. The government should consider increasing corporate income tax rates as a tool for reducing income inequality. Higher taxes on corporate profits can generate more revenue that can be redistributed through social programs and public services.
2. The government should improve tax compliance and enforcement to ensure that capital gains taxes are properly collected. Strengthening the tax administration system can reduce tax evasion and increase revenue.
3. The government should invest in programs that improve access to quality education and skills development, particularly for low-income individuals.

6.3 Suggestion for Further Studies

Scholars who are interested to carry out further studies should do so in the following areas:

1. Investigate the effects of direct taxes on income redistribution across different regions within Nigeria. Regional studies can reveal how tax policies impact income inequality in various local contexts and identify region-specific challenges.
2. Examine how direct taxes affect different income groups, particularly low-income versus high-income households. This can help determine whether tax policies are effectively targeting income redistribution across various income brackets.
3. Perform comparative studies with other countries that have similar tax structures. This can provide insights into how different tax systems impact income redistribution and identify best practices.
4. Evaluate the effects of recent or proposed tax reforms on income redistribution. Analysing how changes in tax policies influence income inequality can provide insights into the effectiveness of reform efforts.

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